

Speculation on Scaling, Maximum Entropy and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics Part 3

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The classical energy conservation equation $KE(x) + V(x) = E$ holds for a quantum bound particle for any energy level if $KE(x)$ is taken to be the average kinetic energy. A quantum bound system differs from classical mechanics in that crests and troughs exist in space (with different heights and base widths). These are described by a function $W(x)$ such that spatial average density = $W(x)W(x)$. We have argued in previous notes that these crests and troughs are a consequence of the crests and troughs in $\exp(ipx)$ (a free particle wavefunction), i.e. in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$.

In this note, we try to understand why a crest and trough bound state pattern should exist based on the ideas of Part 2. In Part 2, we argued that there exists an internal probability in space proportional to p for a spatial event to occur. If one doubles p , this probability doubles and this suggests a halving of the length in which an internal event occurs, i.e. the wavelength.

If one uses the idea of conservation of energy to describe a bound state, then classically at any x there is a $+p(x)$ and a $-p(x)$. If, however, \hbar/p represents a uniform probability length range, then a constant p and $-p$ may occur at different points within this \hbar/p range and so one cannot argue that one has an average of $p-p=0$ in the quantum case. In the quantum situation, one considers all possible p constant values, through $\exp(ipx)$ s, but this complex variable represents uniform probability for a $2 \times 3.14 \hbar/p$ range. In other words, in an energy description with probability, one cannot separate $p(x)$ and $-p(x)$ if these are random variables. This is the reason, we argue, why crests and troughs appear even in the bound situation. In other words, average $p = -i dW/dx / W$ has positive-0 - negative values because of the uniform randomness of $p(x)$ and $-p(x)$ which does not allow them to cancel at an x point (except at the points where the slope $dW/dx=0$).

The Classical and Quantum Bound Problem

Classically, one may describe a bound system in terms of energy through:

$$pc(x)pc(x)/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((1)) \quad \text{Here } pc \text{ is classical momentum}$$

Quantum mechanics, on the other hand, uses $\exp(ipx)$ s to create an average kinetic energy using:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = -1/2m d/dx dW/dx \quad ((2))$$

such that ((1)) holds, but $pc(x)pc(x)/2m$ is represented by ((2)). This leads to a crest-trough pattern for $W(x)$ such that spatial probability $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$.

We try to understand in this note how these crests and troughs appear. In previous notes, we have argued that they are a consequence of $\exp(ipx)$ s, but here we try to use the ideas of Part 2.

Momentum as a Probability

In Part 2, we argued that momentum is proportional to a spatial probability, i.e. for a spatial internal event occurring. If one doubles p , the probability doubles and the spatial length (on average) for an event should halve. This is the idea of $\hbar/p = \text{wavelength}$, we argue. As a result, one may consider a constant p - x range and $-p$ - x range. Classically $p(x)$ and $-p(x)$ cancel, but in this scenario there is a length range \hbar/p which is associated with a uniform probability (as shown by $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. a circle). In other words, a p value may occur anywhere in \hbar/p with uniform probability and a $-p$ may also appear under the same conditions. p and $-p$ will, however, normally not appear at the same x point and so one does not have the notion of p and $-p$ canceling on average as in classical mechanics.

We suggest that due to the probability represented by p and $-p$, one cannot have the forward and backward values cancel for each x , only at periodic points (peaks of $\cos(px)$) and this is ultimately the reason for the crests and troughs in $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ such that:

$$P_{\text{ave}} = -i \frac{dW}{dx} / W \quad ((3))$$

If one simply uses the $\exp(ipx)$ formalism, these ideas, however, may not seem so clear, we argue. It may appear a little confusing that $-idW/dx = 0$ at crest/trough tops and positive and negative values at other places. It is the stochasticity in internal spatial events which lead to such a positive - 0 -negative dW/dx pattern we argue. This is the best one can achieve trying to create the p - $p=0$ at each x of classical physics.

We have argued in previous notes that even $\exp(ipx)$ contains this kind of stochasticity in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ separately because one has a rising slope for each, followed by a flat peak and then a negative slope. In such a case, however, one has motion in only one direction and there is no p and $-p$ canceling as in the classical case, but one may already see the stochasticity. This is linked to the stochasticity of a single p having a probability to be anywhere within \hbar/p with the same probability.

Center-of-Mass Considerations

A bound system represents a localized one and this suggests a center-of-mass, even in quantum mechanics. The overall bound time wavefunction is $\exp(-E_n t)$ which may be extended to $\exp(-iE_n t + i P_{cm} x)$ with $P_{cm}=0$. The crests and troughs of $W(x)$, however, show that $P_{cm}=0$ is an approximation because, due to the stochasticity of each $p, -p$ pair one really has crest pattern with $-idW/dx$ being positive, then 0 and then negative.

Conclusion

In conclusion, a bound quantum problem usually has crests and troughs described by $W(x)$ such that $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$. We have argued in previous notes that this follows from the free particle form $\exp(ipx)$. Here we wish to consider the situation using the ideas of Part II in which we argued that a momentum of p is proportional to the probability of a spatial event occurring in

\hbar/p with uniform probability. This means that classically p and $-p$ cancel at each x point, but do not do so in general in quantum mechanics, only at periodic points, peaks of $\cos(px)$. In other words, one must consider p and $-p$ together because of their stochasticity which leads to positive-0 -negative momentum patterns as shown in $-d/dx \cos(px)$. This follows formally using $\exp(ipx)$, but we argue that one may see it by considering the notion of a uniform spatial probability distribution in a region of \hbar/p which holds for p and $-p$ ensuring that these do not necessarily cancel. This leads to a crest-trough pattern associated with this fluctuating momentum sum due to p and $-p$ following a uniform distribution in \hbar/p . (Overall, all p values are considered, but we focus above on a single constant one, p .)